

Cyclic Products from Thioureas. Part I. A New Method for Nitro-2-imino-2,3-dihydro-4*H*-1,3-benzothiazin-4-ones

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The reaction of methyl and ethyl esters of 2-chloro-3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid with three thioureas has been studied and structures have been assigned to the products.

The reaction of *o*-mercaptobenzoic acid with dicyclohexylcarbodi-imide to afford 2-cyclohexylimino-2,3-dihydro-3-cyclohexyl-4*H*-1,3-benzothiazin-4-one (II: R = cyclohexyl) has been recently reported¹. The reaction goes probably through the intermediate (I: R = cyclohexyl), followed by cyclisation, to yield (II: R = cyclohexyl). The intermediate (I) is actually a *S*-2-carboxyphenyl-*NN'*-dicyclohexylisothiurea.

This suggests that an *S*-arylisothiurea having a -COOR group in *ortho* position to the sulphur atom would cyclise to afford a benzothiazin-4-one of type (II). The stable salts of *S*-alkylisothiureas are usually prepared by the action of thioureas with alkyl halides. The behaviour of thioureas with a halogenobenzene having a mobile halogen atom is expected to be similar. Consequently with a view to obtaining salts of isothiureas, which would furnish isothiureas of type (I) in presence of weak bases and then cyclise to compounds of type (II), the reaction of thiourea with methyl 2-chlorobenzoate containing a labile chlorine has been attempted. The chlorine atom does not, however, seem to be activated by -CO₂Me group to the extent that it may react with thiourea. Methyl 2-chloro-5-nitrobenzoate containing a more labile chlorine (due to activation by -NO₂ and -CO₂Me) also reacts sluggishly with thiourea in presence of potassium acetate to furnish 6-nitro-2-imino-2,3-dihydro-4*H*-1,3-benzothiazin-4-one. In view of these observations, the reaction of methyl 2-chloro-3,5-dinitrobenzoate, which has a more labile chlorine than that in the above ester, with thiourea in dry methanol in presence of potassium acetate has been investigated. The reaction affords a crystalline alkali-soluble compound (A: C₈H₄O₃N₄S) which is identical in all respects to that obtained from ethyl 2-chloro-3,5-dinitrobenzoate under similar conditions. As both the methyl and ethyl esters afford the same product, free of chlorine, the halogen and ester groups seem to have participated in the reaction.

On this basis, it can be assumed that the intermediate, which could not be isolated, may be (III: R=Me or Et) or (IV: R=Me or Et) which, when formed, may cyclise *in situ* to provide the said compound with structures (V) and (VI or VII) (R=H) respectively. The structures (V) and (VI) for (A) are excluded due to the failure to isolate 3,5-dinitro-2-aminobenzoic acid from its hydrolysis with sulphuric acid dihydrate and due to the negative sulphhydryl and thione group tests². Hence compound (A) possesses structure (VII: R=H). On acid hydrolysis, the product (A), however, furnishes a compound (B), $C_8H_5O_6N_3S$, which is soluble in alkali and is identical to that obtained from the reaction of chlorodinitro esters with thiourea in presence of acetic acid. As product (B) possesses one nitrogen atom less and one oxygen atom more than those in (A), it is concluded that it is formed by replacement of -NH in (A) (VII: R=H) by oxygen during hydrolysis. This therefore suggests structure (IX: R=H) for (B). Alkaline hydrolysis of (A) and (B) results in intractable gums.

The reaction of both the methyl and ethyl esters of 2-chloro-3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid with phenylthiourea furnishes the same product (C), $C_{14}H_9O_5N_4S$. Being insoluble in alkali, product (C) is assigned tentatively structure (VIII: R=Ph). The failure to isolate (IX: R=H) by acid hydrolysis of product (C) is also in agreement with structure (VIII: R=Ph) for it.

It is noteworthy that in this case the product is associated with 2,2'-diethoxycarbonyl- and 2,2'-dimethoxycarbonyl-4,4',6,6'-tetranitrodiphenyl sulphides with ethyl and methyl ester respectively.

2. Feigl, "Spot Tests in Organic Analysis", translated by Oesper, Elsevier Publishing Co., 1956, pp. 228, 232.

The chlorodinitro esters (both the methyl and ethyl) react with allylthiourea to furnish the same product, which could have structure either (VII: R=allyl) or (VIII: R=allyl). Some unusual properties, however, are not in accord with these formulations. Further elucidation of its structure is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

6,7-Dinitro-2-imino-2,3-dihydro-4H-1,3-benzothiazin-4-one (VII: R=H).—A solution of thiourea (0.38 g.) in dry methanol (15 ml) was mixed with a solution of methyl 2-chloro-3,5-dinitrobenzoate (1.3 g.) in dry methanol (20 ml) containing anhydrous potassium acetate (0.5 g.). On keeping the mixture for $\frac{1}{4}$ hr. at about 10° and then for 10-12 hr. at the room temperature, the crystalline solid settling was filtered and washed with water and then with hot methanol. The solid (0.84 g.), m.p. 250°, was purified from hot methanol to yield product (A) in white crystals, m.p. 255-57°. On recrystallisation from dimethylformamide, it separated in white shining crystals, m.p. 256-57°. (Found: N, 20.52; S, 12.20. $C_8H_4O_5N_4S$ requires N, 20.88; S, 11.94%).

An identical compound was obtained when, instead of methyl 2-chloro-3, 5-dinitrobenzoate, ethyl ester was used; m.p. and mixed m.p. 256°.

6,7-Dinitro-2H-1,3-benzothiazine-2,4(3H)-dione (IX: R=H).—(i). The compound (A) (0.5 g.) was suspended in 10% H_2SO_4 (10 ml) and enough ethanol was added to dissolve the solid. The mixture was refluxed for 2-3 hr. The red crystalline solid separating was filtered and washed well with water. On crystallisation from ethanol, it yielded 6,7-dinitro-2H-1,3-benzothiazine-2,4(3H)-dione (0.3 g.) in red crystals, m.p. 220°. (Found: N, 15.21; S, 11.65. $C_8H_3O_6N_3S$ requires N, 15.61; S, 11.89%).

(ii). A mixture of methyl 2-chloro-3,5-dinitrobenzoate (1.3 g.), thiourea (0.38 g.), anhydrous potassium acetate (1.5 g.), and glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was refluxed for 1-2 hr. and filtered hot. The filtrate on dilution yielded a red-brown solid which on purification by ethanol yielded a red crystalline compound (0.6 g.); m.p. and mixed m.p. with the above, 218°.

Hydrolysis of Product 'A' with Sulphuric Acid Dihydrate.—The product (A, 0.5 g.) was kept with sulphuric acid dihydrate at 80° for 1 hr. On cooling and dilution with water, an amorphous solid separated. It was collected and treated with aqueous sodium carbonate. The alkaline filtrate on acidification did not furnish any product. All attempts to purify the residue met with failure.

6,7-Dinitro-2-imino-2,3-dihydro-3-phenyl-4H-1,3-benzothiazin-4-one (VIII: R = Ph) was prepared from ethyl 2-chloro-3, 5-dinitrobenzoate (1.3 g.) and phenylthiourea (0.76 g.) according to the procedure described above. The yellow solid obtained was refluxed with ethanol several times till the filtrate was colorless. The residue was purified by dimethylformamide to yield the dinitrophenylbenzothiazin-4-one in fine yellow crystals (0.8 g.), m.p. 285°. (Found: N, 15.87; S, 9.53. $C_{14}H_8O_5N_4S$ requires N, 16.28; S, 9.30%).

On concentration and cooling, the ethanolic extracts yielded 2,2'-diethoxycarbonyl-4,4',6,6'-tetranitrodiphenyl sulphide as a faint yellow crystalline solid (0.1 g.), m.p. 185°. (Found: S, 6.02. $C_{18}H_{14}O_{12}N_4S$ requires S, 6.27%).

If in place of ethyl ester, methyl ester was used, a yellow product was obtained, crystallising from dimethylformamide, m.p. 285°, identical to the above. The mother liquor on dilution yielded 2,2'-dimethoxycarbonyl-4,4',6,6'-tetranitrodiphenyl sulphide as a yellow crystalline solid (0.05 g.), m.p. 263°. (Found: S, 6.52. $C_{16}H_{10}O_{13}N_4S$ requires S, 6.63%).

6-Nitro-2-imino-2,3-dihydro-4H-1,3-benzothiazin-4-one was obtained as above from methyl 2-chloro-5-nitrobenzoate (1.0 g.) and thiourea (0.38 g.) in methanol in presence of anhydrous potassium acetate (0.5 g.). It was crystallised from methanol in microscopic colorless crystals (0.02 g.), m.p. 187-88°. (Found: S, 14.02. $C_8H_5O_3N_3S$ requires S, 14.35%).

The use of ethyl ester instead of methyl ester afforded the same product; m.p. and mixed m.p. 187°.

Reaction of Methyl and Ethyl 2-Chloro-3,5-dinitrobenzoates with Allylthiourea.—The reaction of methyl and ethyl 2-chloro-3,5-dinitrobenzoates with allylthiourea, following the procedure described above, furnished identical products. On crystallisation from methanol or ethanol, it formed light yellow needles, m.p. 197°. (Found: N, 17.98; S, 9.98. $C_{11}H_8O_5N_4S$ requires N, 18.18; S, 10.38%).

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